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INGAME
Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation

INGAME

INGAME – Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation – A holistic approach for a cultural shift in education and policy

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National INGAME Ecosystem of Needs, Practices Target Groups, Stakeholders and Mode of Work Report

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1. Summary

The present report has been prepared in the context of the EU-funded project INGAME (*Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation: A holistic approach for a cultural shift in education and policy*) as part of the work planned under Work Package 2. It is the result of the collaboration between the two Greek partners of the INGAME consortium, namely Symplexis and the Educational Association Anatolia. It concerns both primary and secondary research findings that were collected between the period April – June 2020. In more specific, Symplexis undertook the secondary research work along with the online survey with stakeholders, while the Educational Association Anatolia took the lead in the online survey with youth representatives and the main target group (youth 18-35 years). The final compilation of the report was conducted by the research team of Symplexis.

As we will have the chance to elaborate in detail in the following, the Greek case scenario still has a lot space to cover in terms of online civic engagement initiatives. Some bright examples appear, yet in the most part they originate from the private sector, while the majority of the field research participants seemed to be unaware of good practices related to the use of new technologies for the purposes of civic engagement and sensitization about social and political life related issues in Greece and Europe in general. All in all, these findings pinpoint the importance of the anticipated results of the INGAME project for the empowerment of the future generation in our country as a way to move forward, promote collaboration and facilitate engagement on all fronts.

2. Introduction

The Greek education system is primarily characterized by its versatile nature owing to the multiple laws and decrees that govern it as a result of the numerous changes that each new government introduces in an effort to modernize the existing pedagogical framework in accordance with EU and international standards. As a consequence, Greece today has a multi-layered education system that caters for all students in the country and serves multiple purposes closely linked to key cross-cutting issues that affect the life and wellbeing of the Greek youth and the society at large. To a great extent, this concerns the fields of civic engagement, social and gender equality as civic learning and awareness among children and youth is widely recognized as the cornerstone for creating a democratic society with actively engaged citizens.

The purpose of the present report is to investigate the current state-of-play in Greece with regard to the four key elements central to the INGAME theory of change that WP2 (Mapping the INGAME Ecosystem of Needs, Practices Target Groups, Stakeholders and Mode of Work) of the EU-funded project: “Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation - A holistic approach for a cultural shift in education and policy” aims to define; namely:

- a) civic engagement;
- b) social inclusion;
- c) gender equality; and
- d) game-based informal learning.

Considering the broad spectrum that these fields cover, we note that this report does not aim at providing exhaustive information about each one of the abovementioned fields, but rather offer an overview of the main characteristics of the Greek system that will be then used for the compilation of the transnational – comparative report that will guide the development process of the INGAME products and materials.

In the following, an overview of each targeted field is provided, along with an informative analysis of the needs of the main target group (youth 18-35 years). At the end of this document, a sample of good practices is provided coupled with useful recommendations that should be taken into consideration in the upscaling process that the INGAME project will deliver.

3. Key findings from the Desk Research

3.1 Civic Engagement

Civic engagement in Greece is closely linked to the evolution of the third sector (civil society) and voluntarism, which despite its origin in the principles of democratization and solidarity, until today remains very weak at national level. This is attributed to a number of factors, as Greece has one of the most centralized systems in Europe and OECD countries, where the state on the one hand and the Orthodox Church on the other greatly influence both the social activity and the education, which suffer from politicization and a lack of policy continuity¹. This, along with the limited support that Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) receive from the State (incl. the lack of tax incentives) and the existence of a family-based mentality that builds on the network of relatives instead of community support in terms of mutual aid, solidarity and cooperation (mostly due to a generalized lack of social trust among Greek citizens) have limited the density and strength of the civil society in Greece, far behind from other EU countries². From an empirical point of view, we may observe that voluntarism in the light of civil society work is broadly considered as an institutionalized activity by Greeks (esp. for the older generations, which refers to the generations prior to the Generation X), while philanthropy and particularly the work that the Greek Orthodox Church offers is more deeply embedded in Greek people's lives and often occur spontaneously.

Characteristic is the fact that, to date, a clear definition of civil society and/or voluntary organizations is still lacking, as well as of a central registry of CSOs/NGOs. No reliable data exist as to the number of third sector organisations in Greece, the number of volunteers and their profile, their geographical spread and other such key issues that could provide a clearer picture of civic engagement trends in the country. In fact, the heterogeneity of what we call civil society in Greece is also reflected in the number of different registries that have been established over the years for NGOs/CSOs most of which have had very limited impact as to the actual evolution of the sector. This involves among other:

- the National Agency for Volunteering Citizen in Deed (Ergo Politon) that was established in 2005 with the aim to maintain an up-to-date database of civil society and voluntary organisations;
- the relevant registry of CSOs/NGOs involved in the provision of health and social care services that the Ministry of Health and Social Solidarity maintains since 2001;
- the registry of Greek voluntary organisations, which are involved in offering international assistance and development aid maintained by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs;
- the volunteering portal *www.anthropos.gr* which also maintains a database of NGOs in a number of areas;
- and other.³

Although the general impression is that in the past few decades, civic engagement activities and interventions have increased -especially since the beginning of the financial crisis- this does not reflect a change in social

¹www.sgi-network.org/2019/Greece/Social_Policies

²Huliaras, A. (2014). Creating Civic Engagement from the Top: The dynamics of civil society in Greece. Retrieved from the internet on April 1, 2020 from: [www.uop.gr > images > files > huliaras](http://www.uop.gr/images/files/huliaras)

³EC (2009). Study on Volunteering in the European Union. Country Report Greece. Retrieved from the internet on April 1, 2020 from: [ec.europa.eu > citizenship > pdf > national_report_gr_en](http://ec.europa.eu/citizenship/pdf/national_report_gr_en)

norms, but rather it is mostly attributed to the funding opportunities offered to NGOs/CSOs by donors and particularly by the European Commission, which basically introduced the importance of an active citizen in modern societies. Notwithstanding the positive increasing trend of civic engagement initiatives at national level, a robust civic education policy and mentality is still missing and a close link between civil society and political interest is still widely observed (in the sense of *institutionalised* opportunities for civic engagement and participation).

Education holds a key role in the political socialization and civic education of children in Greece, yet, it remains a question whether the current education system has the capacity to form conscientious and active citizens. A recent research (2017⁴) on pedagogical practices by students of education faculties revealed that more systematic effort is needed to promote the principles of civic education in the school environment, both in terms of sound teaching methodologies and curricula as well as to the targeted training of education staff.

Evidently, Greece still needs to make a lot of progress in the field of civic engagement on the basis of a strong civic education policy framework, yet as we will discuss in the following sections (Section C: Best Practices) there are some promising civic engagement initiatives and programmes that have been adopted in the last few years that show the way forward in promoting active citizenship in Greece in a meaningful way.

3.2. Social inclusion

Traditionally, Greece's social policy has been one of the weakest in Europe, which due to the economic and migration crises has only worsened in the past few years. At policy level, Greece's social inclusion strategy for the different population groups at risk of exclusion and marginalization has been characterized by the lack of continuity in the strategic framework that has been adopted in different time intervals. A number of strategic documents that have been introduced at different stages in the past have failed to generate the desired impact at societal level, which is why we identify many strategic documents that either haven't been renewed and/or even have been literally abandoned due to the lack of available funds and/or political interest and will. This fact in many cases follows the pace of the European Union's initiatives which is why 2020 is considered a landmark year as the main social inclusion strategies currently in place will become obsolete at the end of this year (i.e. 2020) and thus would require follow-up.

These follow up actions concern the umbrella National Strategy on Social Inclusion 2015 – 2020, which is supplemented by other more specialized strategic plans catering for the needs of specific target groups, such as the National Strategy for the inclusion of Roma 2012 – 2020. These strategies aim at improving the grim situation in the social inclusion field that the country's strained economy has created mainly as a result of the financial crisis. However, the Sustainable Governance Indicators (SGI) 2019 Country Report for Greece⁵ show that little progress has been achieved, as despite the slight improvement in the country's ranking since 2014 (by 0.5 points) Greece still falls into the bottom ranks (rank 37 among 41 countries) with regard to social policies.

⁴Konstantinidou et al (2017). Education for Citizenship in Primary Education of Greece: Proposals for Pedagogical Practices by Students of Education Faculties. *International Journal of Learning and Development*, 7 (1), 41-61.

⁵www.sgi-network.org/2019/Greece/Social_Policies

The following graphs (Graphs 1 & 2) showcase Greece's performance in a number of social policy related areas, where evidently there is still much room for improvement.

Greece | Social Policies

SGI 2019 | Greece

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Greece | Social Policies

SGI 2019 | Greece

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Graphs 1&2: Gender equality performance in Greece

Greece's weak performance mainly relates to the fact that the long crisis has badly exacerbated poverty and social exclusion, especially among youth that to a large extent remain excluded from the labour market, with the reported NEET (Not in Education, Employment or Training) share being one of the worst in the OECD. This in fact reflects the persistent tendency of the Greek governments to cater to the social needs of old-age pensioners much more than of any other category of welfare state beneficiaries and especially young people, which explains also the drain brain phenomenon that the country has witnessed in the past years. And despite the fact that Greece is not ranked among the worst-performing OECD countries with regard to income inequality or poverty, social exclusion is unusually high for an EU country (share of Greeks at risk of poverty/ social exclusion was as high as 32% in 2018 according to the Hellenic Statistical Office⁶ - which accounts for over 1 third of the total population - whereas the EU-28 average for the same period was 22,5%).

On the positive side, since early 2017, the government has implemented a minimum income guarantee program called Social Solidarity Income (KEA) that is based on three pillars:

1. income support;
2. access to social services and goods; and
3. provision of support services for (re)integration into the labour market.

Yet this was realized only after considerable delays and without having secured the continuation of this scheme's funding.⁷

⁶Hellenic Statistical Authority (2019). 2018 Survey on Income and Living Conditions. Press release risk of poverty 212018 Survey on Income and Living Conditions. Retrieved from the internet on April 3, 2020 from: [www.statistics.gr > documents](http://www.statistics.gr/documents)

⁷Ibid

3.3. Gender equality

Similar to the other fields under investigation in this report, Greece’s performance in the gender equality field is rather unsatisfactory compared to the rest of Europe. According to EIGE (2019⁸), Greece holds the last place in the EU on the Gender Equality Index with the highest scores recorded in the fields of health and money, whereas the lowest scores are documented in the domain of power as shown in the figure that follows (Graph 3).

Index score for Greece v for 2019 v

Graph 3

In fact, Greece’s gender equality performance has increased by only 4.4 points from 2005 to 2017 that has placed the country in one position lower than in 2005. The slow progress of Greece in the gender equality field compared to the EU-28 average (51.2 points compared to 67.4) has triggered the adoption of the National Strategy and Action Plan on Gender Equality 2016 – 2020 by the General Secretariat for Gender Equality of the Greek Ministry of Interior in 2016 - that replaced the former National Action Plan on Gender Equality for 2010-2013 – followed by the recent (on 26-3-2019) adoption of the new law number 4604 on substantive gender equality and Sexual Gender-Based Violence (SGBV).

The National Action Plan on Gender Equality 2016 – 2020⁹ is aligned with the priorities and objectives of the European Commission in the field of gender equality. It includes a series of both horizontal and vertical

⁸EIGE (2019). Gender Equality Index 2019. Greece. Retrieved from the internet on April 3, 2020 from: eige.europa.eu/publications/gender-equality-index-2019-greece

⁹Greek Ministry of Interior. Gender Secretariat of Gender Equality. National Action Plan on Gender Equality for 2016–2020. Retrieved from the internet on April 3, 2020 from: www.isotita.gr/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/National-Action-Plan-for-Gender-Equality-2016-2020.pdf

interventions across the range of public policy where persistent inequalities exist. To that end, in line with the EC's guidelines, the National Gender Equality covers the following priority axes:

- Social inclusion and equal treatment of women who suffer multiple discrimination;
- Gender-based violence;
- Labour market, family and work life balance;
- Education, training, culture, sports and the media;
- Health;
- Decision making centers.

Despite the Strategy's ambitious objectives and targets, limited progress has been achieved to date as recent statistics reveal, which has prompted the reinforcement of the Greek legislation in the field of gender equality on the basis of the adoption of Law 4604/2019 on Substantive Gender Equality, Preventing and Combating Gender-Based Violence¹⁰ in March 2019. The new Law activates a number of provisions aimed at the implementation of the principle of equal treatment of sexes, gender mainstreaming and the formulation of a network of permanent structures across the country for the prevention and elimination of violence against women in accordance with the Greek Constitution, EU Directives, international Conventions ratified by the Greek State, as well as the Greek family law, the labour law and the social security law.

Among the most important provisions of this Law we distinguish the following:

- The institutionalization of the PanHellenic SGBV network which consists of dedicated Counselling Centers, Hostels, a 24-hour SOS 15900 hotline by the General Secretariat for Gender Equality and the Greek Local Government Authorities (Municipalities).
- The encouragement of public and private enterprises to adopt and implement "Equality Plans" and the introduction of "Equality Labels" that may be awarded by the competent authority of the Greek Ministry of Interior (General Secretariat for Gender Equality).
- The incorporation of the use of gender-neutral language in official documents as a distinctive task of the public administration.
- The institutionalization of the system of quota 40% in favour of women for the lists of candidates in each electoral prefecture at the parliamentary elections.
- The establishment of Autonomous Equality Offices in all Greek Regions (13 in total).
- The reinforcement of the principle of gender mainstreaming in the fields of health and social solidarity with special focus on vulnerable categories of women, such as migrant and refugee women.
- The activation of special provisions against gender stereotypes and discrimination in mass media and advertisement.

Particularly important for the purposes of the INGAME project is the adoption of special provisions in the field of education (primary, secondary and tertiary education) aimed at the elimination of gender stereotypes and the build-up of healthy attitudes among the future Greek adult citizens¹¹. This involves the adoption of a gender-sensitive language in all educational curricula and materials, the promotion of gender equality in career

¹⁰Law 4604/2019 on Substantive Gender Equality, Preventing and Combating Gender-Based Violence. Retrieved from the internet on April 3, 2020 from: www.isotita.gr/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/N.4604-gia-tin-ousiastiki-isotita-ton-fylon.pdf

¹¹General Secretariat for Gender Equality (2019). www.isotita.gr/en/new-legislation-greek-government-substantive-gender-equality-sgbv-athens-march-2019/

guidance, the development and implementation of information sharing and awareness raising programmes on the elimination of gender stereotypes and discrimination for teachers and educators and the promotion of gender equality in all aspects of higher education.

These indeed constitute a positive development in the field of gender equality, yet in order to be effective it should be accompanied by concrete measures and policy interventions in the targeted sectors, especially since the National Strategy and Plan on Gender Equality is due to end at the end of this year (2020).

3.4. Game-based learning

In Greece, the incorporation of Web 2.0 technologies in the education field, both formal and informal, is still in its infancy with most of the relevant initiatives taking place in the private sector and/or in the context of lifelong learning initiatives implemented primarily as part of EU-funded projects. The timing of the writing of this report could not be more relevant as Greece, having an outmoded education system, was confronted with an internal crisis having to rapidly adapt to the new reality that the Coronavirus situation created with the Greek education system struggling to catch up with the requirements of distance/ online learning. To that end, the educational community in Greece largely reported the existence of a non-functional system of distance learning with the big bulk of the institutional efforts placed on the continuation of learning for the last level of secondary education, which is linked to the exams for entering tertiary education (which in the Greek case usually involves a huge financial investment by the student's family as the majority of children attend private classes in order to replace the gaps of the public education system).

Only recently, the Greek research community has started studying the evolution of technology from a space of info searching (web 1.0) into a space of content creation and collaboration among users (web 2.0). In the education field, this is understood as an investment in a broad range of newly created learning opportunities that would allow students, especially those with fewer opportunities to take advantage of broader and more quality access to education resources, which in the long term may be translated into better learning outcomes.

Yet again, the topic under investigation has been very superficially examined from a research point of view. From the available bibliography, we distinguish certain interesting findings mostly relating to the review of the available literature¹², but also to the learning of foreign languages¹³ (which in Greece is primarily private-driven as the quality of foreign language education in public schools is considered rather poor). The findings of these studies show that although Web 2.0. based learning could greatly contribute to the upgrading of the Greek education system, an equally great deal of challenges remains in order for this to become a reality. In fact, although the majority of the teachers, educators and trainers in Greece see positively the integration of Web 2.0. technology in the school curriculum, most of them also point out the lack of readiness of the Greek system to achieve this both in terms of infrastructure, pedagogical methodology and mentality.

As mentioned above, the most promising examples of game-based learning in Greece to refer to originate from EU-funded projects in which Greece has also been represented either from public, or from private organisations (the latter in the form of civil society organisations and/or education actors such as VET schools

¹²Anastasiades, P. S., & Kotsidis, K. (2013). *The Challenges of Web 2.0 for Education in Greece: A Review of the Literature*. *International Journal of Web-based Learning and Teaching Technologies (IJQLTT)*, 8(4), 19-33.

¹³Tzotzou, M. (2018) Integrating Web 2.0 technologies into EFL learning in the Greek state-school context: A mixed-method study. *Research Papers in Language Teaching and Learning*, 9/1 (2018) 32-55.

are usually more often represented in this kind of initiatives). Some of the most characteristic examples in this regard involve the following projects and initiatives:

- The “**ENTRINNO – Online game for entrepreneurship and innovation**”¹⁴ project, which was implemented and evaluated in 8 different EU countries and involved the development of an online game teaching curriculum for youth on entrepreneurial skills-building.
- The “**Digital Responsible Citizenship**”¹⁵ project, which was represented in Greece by a public private school in Greater Athens (Rafina city). The specific project aimed at improving students’ and teachers’ digital citizenship and competency by using game-based learning technologies in line with several components of the digital citizenship framework in Greece and Europe.
- The “**I-Decide**”¹⁶ project which aims at promoting evidence-based policy making through the development of an innovative game-based toolkit accompanied by a relevant mobile app. The focus in this case is the elimination of disparities in learning outcomes and marginalization by supporting school leaders, school staff, and policymakers to engage in shared and inclusive decision making.

These are indeed positive examples to relate with and follow-up, yet it remains an issue of great concern that such initiatives are not at all linked to the formal education system in Greece, which is public and rather old-fashioned and fragmented as many experts in the field report.

¹⁴www.entrinno.org

¹⁵digital-citizenship.org

¹⁶www.idecide-project.eu

4. Training Needs Assessment

4.1 Research sample

Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, it was considered impossible to conduct focus groups in order to reach out to the target group and youth stakeholders, therefore it was jointly decided by the consortium to replace the focus group discussions with online semi-structured questionnaires via google forms. The primary target group of the research consists of young people between 18 and 35 years' old who were asked a number of questions regarding gamification and civic engagement through semi structured online questionnaires.

All in all, 3 online questionnaires were used based on the common research protocol that the INGAME partnership agreed upon for the purposes of Work Package 2. The three questionnaires were translated in Greek by the two Greek partners and distributed widely among their networks. In line with the initially set targets, the first questionnaire was distributed to 5 young individuals, 3 females and 2 males from different age groups as shown in Graph 4 below (for more details, see Appendix 1: Q1 Evaluation Grid).

What is your age?

5 responses

Graph 4 Q1 age group of respondents

Four out of five respondents appeared to be actively engaged in study or work activity. In more specific, only one was engaged in work, while the remaining three were students.

The second questionnaire was addressed to stakeholders in which case, six stakeholder representatives were asked to answer a semi-structured interview questionnaire, primarily online, due to the Covid-19 restrictions (slightly exceeding the initial target of 5 representatives). All online research participants were females, which is quite common for the Greek case (i.e. women are always more willing to participate in research, while the professional fields addressed are by far more female-dominant than male). The stakeholder participants represented two main groups, namely the 26-30 age group (50%) and the 36-45 age group (50%) (Graph 5). As shown below (Graph 6), half of the respondents work in public institutions and social services, two in civil society organizations and one in an international organization. According to the research findings, the views, experiences and attitudes of the stakeholders have been incorporated in the recommendations section (for more details, see Appendix 2: Q2 Evaluation Grid).

What is your age?

6 responses

What is the type of your organization? Please select from below.

6 responses

Graph 5 & 6 Stakeholder demographics & sector

Finally, online Questionnaire 3 was disseminated to a sample of 30 target group representatives (18-35 years old) comprising a differentiated set of questions.¹⁷ The majority of the respondents were females (60%; i.e. 18 participants), while the rest (40%; i.e. 12 participants) were males. Graph 7 below depicts the age group categories that the participants belonged in, while Graph 8 presents the study or work activity they were currently engaged in.¹⁸

¹⁷Finally, six stakeholders, professionals working in youth-related organizations and institutions, complemented the needs assessment and, mainly, the recommendations toward game-based educational activities for civic participation and social inclusion with their responses (Questionnaire 2). This group's demographics are described in the Recommendations section.

¹⁸Initially, the number of responses to Questionnaire 3 were 31. During the analysis it was noted that an answer was duplicated, possibly due to double submission by one respondent. Specifically, answers 30 and 31 were identical. To this end, response 31 was removed from the data.

What is your age?

31 responses

Graph 7 Target group respondents age group

In more specific, the vast majority appeared to be engaged in some kind of work or study activity. 13 out of 30 participants reported some kind of activity related to tertiary education (i.e. higher vocational education and university), while almost an equal number (14 out of 30) mentioned that they are engaged in work activity. Only 1 participant appeared to be engaged in post-secondary education, while 2 of the interviewees did not respond to the question (for more details, see Appendix 3: Q3 Evaluation Grid).

If yes, which one?

29 responses

Graph 8 Q2 participants' engagement

4.2 Needs analysis

Based on the findings of the needs assessment exercise in Greece, both positive and critical voices on the use of technology in promoting social inclusion and equal participation were raised. Notwithstanding the negative attitudes towards the use of technology in these fields, the vast majority appeared to be positively inclined toward the utilisation of ICT as a powerful mean to enhance accessibility to information and promote communication.

In this respect, the research participants claimed that new technologies could facilitate the online engagement of vulnerable groups, boost mobilisation and unification of citizens through awareness raising campaigns, and information sharing in a quicker and more efficient way. It should be noted though that a relatively small part of the research sample expressed concern toward social media activity as a way to mislead and manipulate citizens and especially youth.

It is noteworthy that the Greek research participants are mostly unaware of digital equipment, mobile learning technologies and innovative approaches (such as Serious Games) as tools for youth training in civic engagement. The few ones who appeared to be familiar with such tools named primarily educational games for kids and games created through EU funded projects.

Part of the research sample appeared to believe that existing practices and interventions for promoting young civic engagement, social inclusion and gender equality are usually ineffective due to their mostly informative nature that does not necessarily inspire young adults to act towards common good and the benefit of their community. Nevertheless, young people's engagement in the public social and/or political spheres is seen as an important aspect of a democratic society, hence relevant action to stimulate civic engagement and promote more democratic mind-sets and practices among youth is considered a must.

In that regard, gamification as a tool for civic engagement is primarily considered as a positive prospect though few of the participants expressed skepticism toward that end. Along the same lines, some of the research participants appeared to believe that games can help youth to visualize and better understand socio-political concepts and circumstances and motivate citizens to be further engaged in civic action. There is however, a concern that games alone cannot necessarily develop the type of critical thinking skills that are required for active civic engagement and a few members of the target group noted that they are not aware of any tangible evidence that support the idea that playing digital games in general is directly linked to an active civic or political engagement (even though they believe they can help in this direction especially if their themes and storyboards are relevant).

On top of that, the respondents were asked to suggest the types of activities they believe that should be delivered in order to increase participation of young adults in public life as well as their civic engagement. Education, both formal (through school curricula, theoretical discussions, workshops and lectures by academics and experts) and informal (through service learning programs,¹⁹ volunteering in NGOs or local government initiatives), was primarily mentioned in the participants' responses provided that the goal is to give voice to the youth, empower them to speak publicly and have their opinions on public matters heard by governments.

When it comes to creating an online game for civic engagement the target group members appeared to consider it as a very good idea and most of them suggested that such a game should be designed on the basis of interactions and grounded on problem-solving features, especially when it comes to addressing societal issues. According to our research sample, such a game should place attention on actual problems around the globe, allowing youth stakeholders to understand political and social concerns in a clear yet entertaining way. It is suggested that a game of the sort of INGAME could be used in order to promote cultural values and human rights, reduce stereotypes and prejudice, and develop critical thinking. The skills that can be developed through game playing are regarded as having a positive connection to a range of civic outcomes.

¹⁹Service learning is a particular pedagogy that aims to balance the process of knowledge and learning with service to the community.

5. Good Practices

Evidently, Greece does not have many best practices to showcase, yet there are few bright examples, particularly in the field of civic engagement, that are worth sharing.

Specifically, we distinguish three noteworthy case scenarios (i.e. promising practices in the fields relevant to the INGAME project); namely, the **City of Errors** platform (Good practice 1) the **Vouliwatch** project (Good practice 2) and the **Active Citizens Fund** (Good practice 3) that are presented in more detail as follows. It should be noted that the first two Good Practices were identified through the secondary research analysis, while the last one was highlighted by one of the stakeholder representatives/ interviewees.

5.1 Good practice 1: City of Errors

The City of Errors initiative involves a cross-media platform that aims at combining the documentary genre with the principles of mobile gaming in order to make problem solving an entertaining activity. It has been created during the years of the financial crisis in Greece (2011 – 2014) when nothing seemed to work well in the metropolitan Greek cities and especially in greater Athens that hosts half of the Greek population of approximately 11 million. The platform has two main components, which involve:

- a) A web-documentary series titled “Life in a City full of Errors” that is based on everyday storytelling about the problems that the citizens face presented from the side of the people who try to actually deal with the problems in question.
- b) A mobile iOS application aimed at promoting the direct participation of citizens in the alleviation of everyday problems. The use of the application requires login with a Facebook account that allows the uploading, categorization, geolocation and sharing of photo-stories about the actions that the users engage in in order to fix the identified city problems. To date, a number of relevant actions have been uploaded with some of the most popular tags branded with keywords such as: #solidarity #equality #animal rights #education #get together #urban.

See: cityoferrors.com/new

5.2 Good practice 2: Vouliwatch

This is another relatively recently born initiative in Greece that aims at boosting civic engagement, yet from a rather different angle. Vouli means "Parliament" in Greek, which signifies the focus of this project on political participation. Traditionally, political participation among Greek youth is very low. The Vouliwatch initiative offers a digital platform for Greek citizens to engage in dialogue and publicly question both the Members of the Greek Parliament and the Members of the European Parliament focusing on Greek representatives. This project has been loosely modelled on similar initiatives that are running successfully in other EU and third countries (Ireland, Luxemburg, Tunisia, Germany, France and Austria) and has been widely acknowledged as an effective way to hold the elected representatives of the Greek citizens liable for their parliamentary activity.

See: vouliwatch.gr

5.3 Good practice 3: Active Citizens Fund

The specific Fund (i.e. Active Citizens Fund) is supported through a grant from Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway as part of the EEA Grants 2014 – 2021. The Fund Operator for the Active Citizens Fund in Greece is the Bodossaki Foundation in consortium with the organization Solidarity Now. The overall aim of the initiative is to strengthen civil society, increase citizen participation in civic activities along with support for human rights including minority rights, promote gender equality, and empower vulnerable groups. It develops networks and platforms among CSOs, while being founded on democratic procedures and promoting the sustainability and capacity of the civil society sector in Greece.

See: www.activecitizensfund.gr

6. Recommendations

Based on the opinions and views of a significant number of the surveyed groups in Greece, digital technology and gamification (e.g. role-playing games where participants will be rated by their peers for their positive or negative contribution to a common goal) can play an important role in promoting social inclusion and equal participation. According to the feedback gathered from the stakeholder interviews (i.e. online questionnaires) the respondents appeared to believe that awareness raising and social media campaigns, festivals, webinars offered by educational institutions, art contests, individual and group sessions, and other such activities aiming at civic engagement combined with fun and entertaining activities may increase young people's sense of understanding about public life.

When asked to propose the features that they would consider key in a digital tool such as the one that INGAME project aims at producing, Greek stakeholders suggested that it should necessarily have a good and engaging storytelling and that it should definitely be user friendly, with nice graphics and gender-sensitive avatars, including decision making options that would promote cultural diversity.

The findings of the primary research in Greece corroborate the evidence gathered by relevant literature²⁰, which implies that the integration of Web 2.0. technologies in the Greek education system should be made through a multi-channel approach to increase motivation and achievement of the desired learning objectives. Although such remarks have been primarily made for the field of foreign language learning, our research's findings verify the fact that this need horizontally applies to the formal education system in general in the Greek context.

Linked to the above is the observation that in Greece, concrete evaluation policies are needed in relation to the existing school curriculum in order to overcome the persisting barriers to the integration of modernized technology and/or game-based learning materials in the formal education system. To that end, it is of great importance to improve the teaching context in Greece as a whole through more flexible classroom/desk organization, as well as via the equipping of the Greek school with efficient technological equipment and facilities.

Last but not least²¹, much emphasis should be placed by the central government (Ministry of Education) on the training policies for primary and secondary teachers and educators about the effective use of Web 2.0. technologies in the physical, but also in the online classroom. Additional knowledge on Web 2.0 practices is needed in order for teachers to be able to create innovative pedagogical tools and solutions for all learning fields. Such training should be systematic and should also be accompanied by the strengthening of the role of the school advisors' role, which at present is very much undermined in Greece.

As implied previously, the findings of the present national research are in accordance with the current situation in the Greek education system that in the wake of the 2020 Coronavirus pandemic faced difficulties in managing online/distance learning, both from the side of educational authorities and teaching staff who struggled to cope with the challenges of technology-enabled learning environments. On a more positive note,

²⁰Tzotzou, M. (2018) Integrating Web 2.0 technologies into EFL learning in the Greek state-school context: A mixed-method study. *Research Papers in Language Teaching and Learning*, 9/1 (2018) 32-55.

²¹Ibid

it is anticipated that this experience will act as a learning process for the Greek education system that undoubtedly still has large room for improvement and modernization.

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8. Annexes

8.1 Annex 1: Questionnaire 1 – Evaluation Grid

Evaluation grid: questionnaire 1 (youth group)	
Partner	Ekpaideutikos Omilos Anatolia (Educational Association Anatolia)
Age profile of the participants in questionnaires <i>(please insert the number of people belonging to each age / age group)</i>	<p>18–20: 1 21–25: 2 26–30: 1 31–35: 1</p> <p>What is your age? 5 responses</p> <p>Legend: ● 18-20 years ● 21-25 years ● 26-30 years ● 31-35 years</p>
Number of participants in online research and their gender split	<p>Females: 3 Males: 2</p> <p>What is your gender? 5 responses</p> <p>Legend: ● Female ● Male</p>

Are you currently engaged in a study or work activity?

5 responses

If yes, which one?

4 responses

In minimum 2 pages and maximum 4 pages:

Question N°	Common theme	Contrasting findings
What does civic engagement mean to you?	The interviewees share common ideas of what civic engagement mean to them. Generally, they mentioned the importance of civic engagement in the community and politics. More specifically, they agree that civic engagement shapes and benefits the community. What they also have in common that they believe there is an obvious link between the political aspect of societies and civic engagement. They believe that civic engagement makes civil society stronger, democracy healthier, and provide solutions to public matters.	There are no contrasting findings within the responses.

	<p>KEYWORDS: community, democracy, common good, political sphere, public matters.</p>	
<p>What kind of activities do you think should be delivered to increase the participation of young adult in public life in general and more specifically, their civic engagement?</p>	<p>There are similar opinions among the interviewees. The responses consist of ideas about workshops and activities that will give a voice to young adults to empower them to participate in civic engagement. They share the view that education plays a crucial role in increasing young adult participation in civic engagement. A very popular opinion in the data collected is that school can help a lot in increasing youth participation in public life. According to the interviewees school can organise educational programs that will help young people realize the importance of civic engagement. For the interviewees is also crucial that young adults are given chances to speak in public and express themselves about public matters.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: education, schools, workshops, empowering, public life</p>	<p>There are no contrasting findings within the responses.</p>
<p>Do you know any policies, practices and interventions for promoting young civic engagement, social inclusion and gender equality? If so, should they improve or change?</p>	<p>The data collected for this question reveals some common themes. The interviewees do agree that the existing practices are not enough to achieve the civic engagement of young adults. They claim that many of the existing interventions are not really useful since they just inform the participants about the issues, but they do not lead them to action.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: inspire, public life, improvement, raise awareness, not useful</p>	<p>The data we collected showed some contrasting parts in the participants' responses. Although most of the participants answered that the existing practices are not enough there were also a few answers that noted Erasmus projects and school practices as known policies without commenting on the need for improvement.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: Erasmus programs, school practices</p>
<p>Are you aware of new technologies (digital tools and mobile devices like GPS, PDAs, Tablet PCs, Virtual</p>	<p>Most interviewees respond that they don't know such tools and even if they knew them, they are not aware of their use for civic engagement.</p>	<p>There is a notable contrast in some responses of the interviewees. One of them know that such tools exist, is not persuaded that these tools help the goal of civic engagement. One</p>

<p>Reality, hand-held technologies, mobile learning technologies, etc.) and innovative approaches (like for example Online Gaming, Serious Games, Game-based Learning) that can be used to discuss global issues, like social inclusion and gender equality? If yes, have you ever used them and why?</p>	<p>KEYWORDS: lack of knowledge, lack of use</p>	<p>respondent just use such technologies for entertainment and communication.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: play, communicate, do not actually help</p>
<p>We are developing an online game, called INGAME which will allow users to learn from simulated experience enhancing critical reflection on social and political circumstances, build skills and stimulate interest for collective action. What would an online game like INGAME need to attract your interest? Which features would you like the game to have?</p>	<p>Regarding this question, there are some common themes in the collected responses. The interviewees agree that the game should be based on real life- situations and real-life problems that someone can face. They think that the message should be obvious.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: reality, actual situations, “stop living fairy-tales”</p>	<p>There is a contrasting finding in the responses. While the majority of the interviewees propose focusing mostly on social issues there is one that supports the idea of focusing more on politics and geopolitics.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: geopolitics, interstate affairs, social issues</p>

8.2 Annex 2: Questionnaire 2 – Evaluation Grid

Evaluation grid: questionnaire 2 (stakeholders)	
Partner	Symplexis
Age profile of the participants in questionnaires <i>(please insert the number of people belonging to each age / age group)</i>	<p>18–20: 0 21–25: 0 26–30: 3 31–35: 0 36–45: 3</p> <p>What is your age? 6 responses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 19-25 years 26-35 years 36-45 years 46-55 years Above 55 years
Type of organisation	<p>What is the type of your organization? Please select from below. 6 responses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Youth training institutions International Organizations Youth Organizations Civil Society Organizations Public Institutions and Social Services Local Authorities Other (please specify)
Number of participants in online research and their gender split	<p>Females: 6 Males: 0</p> <p>What is your gender? 6 responses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Female Male

In minimum 2 pages and maximum 4 pages:

Question N°	Common theme	Contrasting findings
<p>Which factors influence the civic engagement of young adult?</p>	<p>More than half of the interviewees agreed that the most important factors for young adults' civic engagement are: education, family, friends, information through mass media and relevant literature. In general, civil society institutions were frequently mentioned.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: social awareness, education, media, family</p>	<p>The rest of the interviewees didn't agree with the fact that civic engagement is a matter of institutions. For them civic engagement depends on each young adult as a personality and is based on each ones' personality traits and motivation. One interviewee noted that the trust to the system is very important factor.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: Personal awareness and interests, motivation</p>
<p>What kind of activities do you think should be delivered to increase the participation of young adult in public life in general and more specifically, their civic engagement?</p>	<p>Most of the participants agreed that the activities that will boost participation of young adults in public life are various types of campaigns and group activities: social media and awareness-raising campaigns, fun activities, competitions, webinars, activities in schools and universities.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: campaigns, activities, local community</p>	<p>There was one slightly contrasting, yet complimentary, answer suggesting that the activities that should take place for young adults' civic engagement depend on the young adults' interests.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: individual interests</p>
<p>What are the main difficulties you face in involving young people in civic engagement activities?</p>	<p>A great number of interviewees claimed that the most common difficulties they face in involving young people in civic engagement are lack of: interest, motivation and knowledge on the sector.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: "lack of motivation, interest, knowledge</p>	<p>According to two interviewees the main difficulties that young adults face in regards to civic engagement are: financial difficulties and cultural and linguistic differences and misunderstandings.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: cultural differences, economic obstacles</p>
<p>In your area of work, do you know of successful initiatives aimed to improve civic participation of young people and their attention to social inclusion or gender equality issues? If so, which are the main</p>	<p>Stakeholders mentioned Vouliwatch (vouliwatch.gr), Active Citizens Fund (www.activecitizensfund.gr/en), Foteini Kypseli (www.fotinikipseli.gr) and integration courses that consist of modules on Greek language learning, cultural orientation, job readiness and life skills Public talks can be an additional initiatives.</p>	<p>N/A</p>

<p>elements of success?</p>	<p>KEYWORDS: group projects, integration learning, public dialogue</p>	
<p>Are you aware of new technologies (digital tools and mobile devices like GPS, PDAs, Tablet PCs, Virtual Reality, hand-held technologies, mobile learning technologies, etc.) and innovative approaches (like for example Online Gaming, Serious Games, Game-based Learning) that can be used to discuss global issues, like social inclusion and gender equality? If yes, have you ever used them and why?</p>	<p>Many interviewees knew the types of technologies mentioned. Have used them in the past often in the context of other EU projects. More specifically, the most popular ones were: online gaming, GPS, virtual reality and mobile devices. A small number of participants, although they were aware of these new technologies, claimed that they haven't used them yet.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: knowledge of new technologies, common use of mobile technologies, popularity of online gaming</p>	<p>Only one stakeholder was unaware of such technologies but they find them a great idea. Another claimed that she have used them but suggests that for civic engagement issues digital tools are not appropriate and that they should be addressed face to face.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: lack of knowledge, disapproval of new technologies' role in the promotion of civic engagement</p>
<p>We are developing an online game, called INGAME which will allow users to learn from simulated experience enhancing critical reflection on social and political circumstances, build skills and stimulate interest for collective action. What would an online game like INGAME need to attract your interest? Which features would you</p>	<p>Most participants recommended that the game should include exciting elements and fun graphics, should be easy to use it, should have a good storytelling, exclude any type of stereotypes, have more female roles and call the players to make decisions. Also, they stated that the game should promote social interacting.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: user-friendly, fun, stereotype-free, decision-making, role-playing</p>	<p>Only one stakeholder noted that she has to first use the game and then make recommendations on its improvement.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: post-use recommendations</p>

<p>like the game to have?</p>		
<p>Do you have additional notes or suggestions that you think could be useful for our research?</p>	<p>Most of the interviewees didn't have any additional notes and suggestions that would improve the research.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: no additional comments</p>	<p>The one stakeholder stated that it should be made clear to which age groups the game will be addressed while another recommended to include places and graphic design not very popular and real life looking (e.g. villages, slums).</p> <p>KEYWORDS: specify age groups, not just real-life situations included</p>

8.3 Annex 3: Questionnaire 3 – Evaluation Grid

Evaluation grid: questionnaire 3 (target group)																
Partner	Ekpaideutikos Omilos Anatolia (Educational Association Anatolia)															
<p>Age profile of the participants in questionnaires <i>(please insert the number of people belonging to each age / age group)</i></p>	<p>18–20: 7 21–25: 13 26–30: 5 31–35: 5</p> <p>What is your age? 31 responses</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Age Distribution Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Age Group</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18-20 years</td> <td>7</td> <td>25.8%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>21-25 years</td> <td>13</td> <td>41.9%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>26-30 years</td> <td>5</td> <td>16.1%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>31-35 years</td> <td>5</td> <td>16.1%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Age Group	Count	Percentage	18-20 years	7	25.8%	21-25 years	13	41.9%	26-30 years	5	16.1%	31-35 years	5	16.1%
Age Group	Count	Percentage														
18-20 years	7	25.8%														
21-25 years	13	41.9%														
26-30 years	5	16.1%														
31-35 years	5	16.1%														
<p>Number of participants in online research and their gender split</p>	<p>Females: 18 Males: 12</p> <p>What is your gender? 31 responses</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Gender Distribution Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Gender</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Female</td> <td>18</td> <td>58.1%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Male</td> <td>12</td> <td>41.9%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Gender	Count	Percentage	Female	18	58.1%	Male	12	41.9%						
Gender	Count	Percentage														
Female	18	58.1%														
Male	12	41.9%														
<p>Q3. Are you currently engaged in a study or work activity?</p>	<p>Yes: 28 No: 2</p> <p>Are you currently engaged in a study or work activity? 31 responses</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Engagement Status Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Yes</td> <td>28</td> <td>93.5%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No</td> <td>2</td> <td>6.5%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Percentage	Yes	28	93.5%	No	2	6.5%						
Response	Count	Percentage														
Yes	28	93.5%														
No	2	6.5%														
<p>Q4. If yes, which one?</p>	<p>Higher vocational education and university: 13</p> <p>Work activity: 14</p> <p>Post-secondary education: 1</p>															

In minimum 2 pages and maximum 4 pages:

Question N°5	Common theme	Contrasting findings
<p>What does civic engagement mean to you?</p>	<p>Most of the answers associate civic engagement with democratic mindsets and practices. I.e. on the one hand, young people both raise key ideas and principles of democracy as they perceive them, e.g. a balanced understanding between rights and responsibilities (“<i>you know your obligations in concert with your rights</i>”) or serving the common good and shared goals; on the other hand, they highlight practical activities and the active form of engagement that matches such a mindset, e.g. voluntarism, bringing about change to one’s community (e.g. “addressing issues for public concern”, or “acting to create a change”) and working for better futures—all this with a problem-solving mentality.</p>	<p>Several answers (4) present a picture of engagement as awareness and information, showing that engagement goes hand in hand with reflection (e.g. “consciousness of people to make a better world”, “[...] to have political knowledge, but not necessarily a crystallized opinion. It means to be aware of the government’s decisions that affect you as a citizen.”)</p> <p>3 answers only focus on political forms of engagement, such as elections and petitions.</p> <p>Only 2 answers conceptualize engagement as an individual, self-referential activity / attitude (e.g. “standing up for my rights, claiming what I think is righteously mine” or “self-discipline, and know how to survive in demanding conditions.”)</p> <p>Finally, 1 answer attributes no substantial value to engagement by calling it “Just a title”</p>
Question N°6	Common theme	Contrasting findings
<p>Have you participated in any of these initiatives in the last two years?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional pressure campaigns - 1 • Flashmob - 2 • Awareness campaigns on social networks - 4 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Petition - 5 • Square demonstrations, marches, sit-in - 8 • None of these - 11 	
Question N°7	Common theme	Contrasting findings
What was the cause? (In answer to Q6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No answer - 12 • University-related issues (e.g. the merging of departments) - 5 • Environmental issues - 4 • Human rights (e.g. anti-racist, anti-fascist) - 4 • Awareness raising (on what issue?) - 3 	With the exception of educational issues (university), a couple of answers only (2) indicate an interest specific to local/regional current affairs that affect Greece directly, e.g. concerning religious activity restrictions during the Covid-19 lockdown and the FYROM renaming to North Macedonia that infringes on the Greek cultural and historical heritage.
Question N°8	Common theme	Contrasting findings
Do you think that technology could play a role in promoting social inclusion and equal participation? If yes, how? If not, why not?	<p><i>Both positive as well as critical voices on the use of technology were raised – positive comments emerge as mainstream</i></p> <p>Yes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology / internet enhances accessibility of information - 7 • Technology is widespread / achieving greater reach - 6 • The communicative power of technology (e.g. online engagement can be less daunting for shy people or vulnerable groups) - 6 • Mobilising and potentially unifying people by promoting campaigns - 5 • Speed of news spread - 3 • For people with impairments (e.g. motor disabilities) - 1 • Technology minimising bureaucracy 1 	<p>No</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concerns over the manipulation and misleading role of social media (e.g. through fake news, echo-chambers), that annuls informed and equal participation. - 3 • Uniform groupings of people, promotion of isolationism and right wing politics (e.g. “echo-chambers”) - 2 • An interesting, somewhat ambivalent comment concerns the legitimisation of messages that are not necessarily valid(?), which become popular through repetition and spread: “Social media play a major role in our lives. We start liking the idea of something when we see it over and over again and then it becomes more familiar” - 1 • Not really - 1
Question N°9	Common theme	Contrasting findings

<p>Are you aware of game-based learning initiatives? If so, could you name these? what do you think?</p> <p><i>(double-barrelled question)</i></p>	<p><i>Most of the respondents didn't know of any examples – yet, 4 out of these respondents commented on the 'what do you think'</i></p> <p>No – 22</p> <p>(On the “what do you think” part)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge retrieval enhanced - 4 • Imagination, fun - 2 • Future-oriented - 1 • Potential to enhance learning in a personalised manner - 1 • Creative component - 1 • Empathic component / seeing other people's perspectives through role-play - 1 	<p>Yes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A foreign language learning, game-based platform called 'Duolingo' - 3 • Erasmus+ associated game platforms - 2 • Drama games (theatre of the oppressed) - 1 • 'Mikrapaidia' & 'Kidmedia' (educational games for primary school children, the latter for SEN children) - 1 • GameLab (MIT) - 1 • ENTRINNO (EU-funded) - 1
<p>Question N°10</p>	<p>Common theme</p>	<p>Contrasting findings</p>
<p>Do you know of any initiatives on young people's civic engagement you consider 'best practices'? If yes, name them.</p>	<p><i>Yes (14) and no (16) answers are more or less balanced. For practical reasons I have placed Yes answers in the opposite column, i.e. in the contrasting findings, also because in most cases no specific 'best practice' initiatives are mentioned.</i></p> <p>No – 16</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Humanitarian / social issues (e.g. disability awareness, support to elderly people, philanthropy, theatre of the oppressed) - 4 • No - 3 • Environmental issues (e.g. tree planting, collecting litter) - 3 • Political issues (council and European Parliament simulations, through Erasmus + projects, student protests) - 3 • Recreational (e.g. TED talks, outdoor activities) - 1 • One too generic answer - Facebook, Wikipedia, Instagram
<p>Question N°11</p>	<p>Common theme</p>	<p>Contrasting findings</p>
<p>How do you think Gamification could be used to enhance critical reflection on social and political circumstances of young adult?</p>	<p><i>Lack of awareness or scepticism, even if respondents are positive</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No answer or “don't know” - 13 • It cannot (any engagement might be evoked involuntarily / unconsciously through engagement with a game) - 1 	<p><i>Positive answers</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generic answers about positive role of gamification overall - 4 • By means of employing user / youth friendly interface (e.g. visualisation techniques) - 3 • By being fun (e.g. role-play) - 3

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is no evidence to support this - 1 <i>(the respondent is otherwise positive on the role of games)</i> • Developing critical thinking is contingent on many factors, e.g. one's age, social environment and broader engagement with issues – it's not an 'outcome' of the engagement with games - 1 <i>(the respondent is otherwise positive on the role of games)</i> • It may invoke competition instead - 1 <i>(the respondent is otherwise positive on the role of games)</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media already play an important role in young people's lives - 1 • With an emphasis on the civic / humanitarian dimension (e.g. by promoting cultural values, human rights, reducing stereotypes) - 1 • By placing focus on strategic thinking in politics, marketing etc. - 1 • By offering a diversity of materials - 1
Question №12	Common theme	Contrasting findings
According to you what are the most successful activities and practices for fostering civic participation, social inclusion and gender equality among young people (i.e. diversity-days with games, workshops, exhibitions, theatre, round-tables/debates, competitions on drawings, photographs, etc.)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All those mentioned / combination of the activities mentioned in the question - 13 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion forums / round tables - 5 • Competitions (e.g. hackathons) - 4 • Arts-based - 4 • Any activity that is free-of-bias and not imposed (e.g. one's ideology) - 2 • Sports based - 2 • Diversity days - 2 • Appropriate role models and a listening mentality (e.g. parents, the church, books) - 1 • Visualisation techniques / documentaries 1 • Community service - 1 • Non-competitive - 1 • Fun and interactive activities - 1
Question №13	Common theme	Contrasting findings
Do you have additional notes or suggestions that you think could be useful for our research?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No answer - 17 • No, I don't have anything to add - 6 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An opportunity through the questionnaire to actually practice one's engagement and voice concerns by suggesting what's most important to him/her (issues other than gamification) - 1

		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Games should focus on freedom of speech and allow people to “mix and match” - 1• You could interview some people who are active in civic engagement and ask them how they first got immersed into this process. (Or design a questionnaire that will be directed towards them?) - 1• The questionnaire could focus on gender uniqueness instead of gender equality - 1
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INGAME

Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation